

Challenges and Problems of Jasmine Cultivators in Udupi District: A Case Study

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Abstract:-

Purpose: Jasmine is South India's oldest fragrance flower and commercial crop. The present study aims at identifying major Challenges and problems of jasmine cultivation in Udupi district.

Design/Methodology/Approach: Undertaking a case study by gathering data from primary and secondary sources and presenting a SWOT analysis on the research topic.

Finding/Result: The study specifies jasmine cultivation is one of the important commercial crops available to the rural masses in order to improve their social and economic standard. It provides employment for the rural mass since it is a labour-intensive unit and plays a major role in the eradication of poverty.

Originality/Value: This study is an attempt to trace the challenges and problems faced by jasmine cultivators.

Paper Type:Case study-based research analysis.

Keywords:- Problems, Challenges, SWOT analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Flowers have had their own significance since ancient times, and they are used for decoration, worship, and to satisfy aesthetic feelings. Flowers have consistently generated consistent demand in worship places and festivals, and the sector benefits from skilled human resources and a trade association. The flowers are highly esteemed for their economic use such as cosmetics, food essences, pharmaceuticals and so on.

Jasmine is one of the earliest known fragrant flowers cultivated by man. It is popularly used in southern India for a variety of decorative and personal purposes. The Udupi jasmine growing community in India's coastal Karnataka is a successful and viable community-based enterprise. Jasmine cultivation contributes significantly to social and economic growth. It facilitates in the promotion of rural economy, food security, and poverty alleviation. The majority of Udupi jasmine is grown in the Shankarapura and surrounding villages of Udupi district of coastal Karnataka, India, including Shirva, Belle, Belman, Kaup, Katapadi, Bantakal, and Innanje. Many of the farmers depend directly on the cultivation of Udupi jasmine for their livelihood (Krishnamurthy MK, Parameshwar NS, Sridhar Herle P, 1995). The cultivators have other sources of income, but jasmine cultivation is their main source of their economy.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

S. No.	Area	Findings	Authors
1	Economic condition	An attempt was made to analyse jasmine cultivators' economic conditions such as income, expenditure, savings, indebtedness, irrigation, and problems. State marketing boards with members that include small and marginal farmers have been formed in many states. They should be given more power and the necessary facilities and resources.	S.Prethesa Mercy & C.Selva Smiley (2019)[3].
2	Constraints faced by jasmine growers	The research study's objectives are to identify the constraints that jasmine growers face using a random sampling method. In order to reduce the problems of jasmine growers, insecticides, pesticides, and biofertilizers should be available on time. More value-added industries based on jasmine, such as perfumery industries, are required. Plants should be available in large quantities from government nurseries at the appropriate time; a cold storage unit is required.	Dr.K.P.Vanetha (2021)[4].
3	Cultivation and marketing constraints jasmine	According to the study, jasmine growers and cultivators are mostly small and marginal farmers who depend largely on market middlemen to sell their produce. Most farmers lack awareness of the market and are illiterate or have limited education. So that they could only make a minimal profit, and sometimes even a loss. As a result, immediate government assistance for agricultural problems is required.	Rajamohan S & Sathish A (2019) [5].

4	Yield gap and constraints in jasmine cultivation	As per the study, small and marginal farmers encounter numerous challenges not just during production but also during marketing. An effort has been made to pinpoint the yield gap, the actual production and marketing issues that farmers actually deal with, as well as the potential for this sector to stabilise productivity. As the crop began to produce in the third year, marketing costs began. The main expense in marketing expenses is the commission charge.	A. Janaki Rani and P.P. Murugan (2020)[6].
5	An economic analysis of cost and return	Among the farmers in the area, the jasmine crop is gaining popularity. The cost analysis revealed that the jasmine growers in Chitradurga district had spent a variety of expenses that indicated the per acre establishment cost and the average maintenance cost were calculated per acre per year. The price of fertilisers and planting supplies was high among maintenance cost.	S. Kumar & P.K. Mandanna (2013)[7].
6	An economic analysis of jasmine cultivation	Jasmine is vital in providing significant employment opportunities to rural residents. As a result, it necessitates deliberate and ongoing attention. The Jasmine cultivators, traders, exporters, government, and others would go a long way in referring to the share of Indian Jasmine in both domestic and foreign markets.	S Thangamayan, S N Sugumar, S Chandrachud (2019)[8].
7	An economic study	Flower cultivators have profited from jasmine cultivation. Cultivators spend less money on production and earn more from jasmine cultivation. They are also increasing production. When compared to other flowers, most cultivators cultivate a higher level of jasmine cultivation. Because people require jasmine for a variety of purposes. The cultivators have chosen jasmine for cultivation in the research area.	R. Latha & Dr. R. Pichumani (2018)[9].

Table 1: Literature review summary

III. RESEARCH GAP

The research gaps in research analysis towards beneficiaries of jasmine farmers leading to rural development and inclusive growth in rural areas leading to an increase in farmers' standard of living and overall development of farmers in rural areas. It is also important to note that there is a research gap among different groups of jasmine growers in terms of their access to microfinance and the impact of various government programmes on their income levels. It was also discovered that no research had been conducted at the gross root level. The current study is being conducted in order to close the gap.

IV. RESEARCH AGENDA

The study's main focus is on the economic empowerment of jasmine farmers and how the SWOT analysis will help to identify and analyse strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats based on the replies of respondents and observations obtained during data collecting. This approach was used to look into the challenges and problems faced by farmers in the Udupi district.

V. OBJECTIVES

The specific objectives of this review study are,

- To study the status of jasmine cultivator.
- To identify the economic condition faced by jasmine flower cultivator in Udupi district.
- To study the achievements of jasmine cultivators in rural area.
- To study the proposed SWOT analysis as jasmine cultivation.

VI. OVERVIEW

A. Udupi jasmine-farm to market

Jasmine is a year-round crop that is typically managed to grow by the entire family. Individuals or entire families cultivate and collect jasmine. Jasmine collection by growers begins early in the morning and concludes by 10 a.m. The collection of jasmine buds is the first step in the process. The buds that are collected are not sold directly to the consumer. Instead, they are tied by a 6-inch chain. These tied chains of buds are then rolled up in banana leaves and a slip with information such as the household name and number of buds is placed inside. These bundles are set aside for "agents" to collect. The agent's responsibility is to collect the buds from the households and then assemble them into commercial units called "chendu" that contain 800 - 805 buds each. Being that not all households will be able to grow the desired number of buds, the agents form these units using whatever buds they have collected from multiple households. Such units are therefore combined to form the "atte" bundle. One "atte" is made up of four "chendus" (bundle). The agents also collect information slips from each household, which the growers place in wrapped banana leaves and store. A separate record is kept with the information of each grower and the price to be given that day. The grower is paid every seven days based on the number of flowers supplied.

VII. METHODOLOGY

The study is being carried out in Shankarapura, Udupi district. This study was conducted using both primary and secondary data. Interviews with jasmine farmers and various agencies dealing with jasmine cultivation and marketing are used to collect primary data. Secondary data was gathered from various online sources, such as websites, books, journals, and article. A qualitative approach has been

adopted for carrying out the case study. In respect to the qualitative approach, subjective assessments of attitude and behavioural changes and interviews were conducted. A sample of jasmine farmers involved in cultivation has been studied. Based on the information gathered, the SWOT analysis was used to examine the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of the jasmine cultivation in Udupi district.

VIII. SWOT ANALYSIS

SWOT analysis is a tool for strategic planning. SWOT analysis investigates the various factors that can be beneficial or detrimental to a plan or entity. Strengths are those elements that give an advantage over competitors in the sector. Weaknesses are factors that disadvantage the sector. Opportunities are favourable circumstances or conditions that are present in the environment. A threat is an unfavourable circumstance or condition that could prevent a

sector from achieving its objectives. Opportunities and threats are typically external in nature, but the sector's strengths and weaknesses are typically internal.

Webber and Labaste (2010) and Rikken(2011) stressed that even though SWOT analysis is not precise tool, it is good way to provide a general characterization of the current state of the industry, identify issue and generate discussion.

The SWOT analysis is used to analyse the Jasmine sector's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats based on respondents' responses and observations made during data collection. SWOT analysis is a qualitative starting point for strategic analysis. The SWOT analysis method was applied thoroughly investigate the challenges and economic conditions of jasmine cultivation in Udupi district.

Fig. 1: SWOT analysis

Source: Author

• **Strengths:** Floriculture is an extremely labor-intensive industry. Jasmine flowers, in particular, necessitate special care and attention from plant growth to marketing. Unskilled labour is ample in India, especially in rural areas. Jasmine cultivation generates significant profits for farmers as well as employment for the farmer community and agricultural labourers. Location, season, and socio-religious occasions, as well as symbolic value, will increase the demand for flower marketing.

Udupi jasmine has a distinct advantage because there is no other variety of Jasmine grown in the immediate vicinity that has a GI tag. Jasmine is India's most important commercial crop. A successful viable community-based enterprise is the Udupi jasmine growing community in India's coastal Karnataka. Despite having other sources of income, jasmine cultivation has provided this community with a consistent source of income. Jasmine cultivation is critical to economic and social

development. It aids in the promotion of rural livelihoods, food security, and poverty alleviation.

- **Weakness:** The majority of jasmine farmers are small and marginal. Small and marginal farmers face numerous challenges not only in cultivation but also in marketing their products. As a result, they are unable to meet the demands of industries and other countries. The major constraints encountered were unavailability and high-cost labour, pest and diseases, monsoon failure, unstable market price, perishability nature, and cold storage facilities.
- **Opportunities:** The demand for jasmine is increasing rapidly due to the rise in living standards and significant changes in people's lifestyles brought on by India's socioeconomic changes. Numerous floriculture projects focused on export are anticipating domestic demand to sell their goods during the slow export season because of the massive rate of increase in domestic demand. A rising demand for flowers on a local, national, and international scale necessitates the development of more value-added industries based on jasmine, such as the perfume and cosmetics industries.
- **Threats:** Climate change, labour shortages, fluctuating sales, low government support, a lack of cold storage units in airports, and unstable conditions are the major threats to jasmine cultivation. The main factors are the quality of the jasmine flowers. Poor-quality flowers will have an impact on both domestic and imported produce.

IX. FINDINGS

- Jasmine growers and cultivators are small and marginal farmers who depend largely on market middlemen to sell their products.
- The jasmine growers face numerous challenges not only during production but also during marketing.
- Jasmine cultivation is gaining popularity among farmers due to its commercial nature and the high rate of profit it provides during certain seasons.
- Jasmine cultivation provides employment opportunities to rural residents; numerous people rely on jasmine cultivation, marketing, and other processes.

X. RESULTS

Following are the results noticed during the research field work:

- Jasmine flowering requires special care and attention, from plant growth to marketing. Hence, if proper care is taken, then crop yield will be naturally high.
- Udipi jasmine is the most important commercial crop. It is a community-based enterprise that provides a consistent source of income.
- It has also been observed that jasmine cultivation promotes social and economic development, resulting in rural development and upliftment.
- It provides employment for the rural mass since it is a labour-intensive unit and plays a major role in the eradication of poverty.
- Proper storage facilities and the usage of modern techniques will definitely boost production and proper

marketing during socio-religious occasions will increase the profit.

- Jasmine cultivation serves as a consistent source of income. It aids the promotion of rural livelihoods and food security, leading to poverty alleviation.

XI. CONCLUSION

In accordance with the results of the study, jasmine cultivation is one of the important commercial crops available to the rural masses in order to improve their social and economic standard. Farmers have realised that banks and the government must provide more and more facilities to improve jasmine production. Instable marketing situations pose a significant threat to large-scale production. Furthermore, pricing must be done in a systematic manner. Also, the presence of middlemen in product marketing must be avoided for growers to maximize profits.

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